

PROJECT DELIVERABLE

Project acronym: **TRUSTyFOOD**

Project title: **Stakeholders-driven pathways for blockchain implementation in the agri-food sector**

Grant Agreement number: 101060534

<i>WP No</i>	<i>Deliverable related No</i>	<i>Deliverable No</i>	<i>Deliverable name</i>	<i>Lead beneficiary</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Dissemination level</i>	<i>Due date</i>
1	D1.2	D2	Data Management Plan (V1)	TCA	DMP	P – Public	31/12/2022

Actual submission date: 27/12/2022 – M06

Funded by
the European Union

Document information

Authors

Raffaello Prugger, Marianna Faraldi, TCA, Italy

Project co-ordinator:

Mr Raffaello Prugger

Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.

Phone: +39 02 67077370

E-mail: r.prugger@tecnoalimenti.com

Work-package 1 Leader

Mrs Marianna Faraldi

Organisation: TECNOALIMENTI S.C.p.A.

Address: Via Gustavo Fara, 39

Phone: +39 02 67077370

E-mail: m.faraldi@tecnoalimenti.com

Project funding

Grant Agreement n.: 101060534 — TRUSTyFOOD — HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-07

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

ABBREVIATION LIST	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. DATA SUMMARY	5
1.1. INTRODUCTION	5
1.2. GUIDING PRINCIPLES: GENERAL PURPOSE FOR RE-USING OR GENERATING OPEN PUBLICLY-FUNDED SCIENTIFIC DATA.....	5
1.3. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN: GENERAL PURPOSE.....	5
1.4. SPECIFIC PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATION OR RE-USE IN RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT.....	6
1.5. BASIC ISSUES THAT WILL BE DEALT WITH FOR THE DATA MANAGEMENT	6
1.6. ORIGIN OF DATA	7
1.7. TYPES OF DATA RE-USED WITHIN THE PROJECT.....	7
1.8. TYPES OF DATA GENERATED WITHIN THE PROJECT	7
1.9. DATA TO BE SHARED AND NOT	8
1.10. DETAILS ON DATA GENERATED.....	9
1.10.1. DATABASE OF PILOTS/ USE CASES.....	9
1.10.2. DATA FROM THE QUESTIONNAIRES/INTERVIEWS WITH USE CASES' REPRESENTATIVES	10
1.10.3. FINDINGS ON BLOCKCHAIN USE FOR TACKLING PROBLEMS IN THE AGRI-FOOD INDUSTRY	11
1.10.4. DATA FROM THE USER AND STAKEHOLDERS' SURVEY	11
1.10.5. A DATABASE OF STAKEHOLDERS CONTACTS	11
1.10.6. DATA COLLECTED INSIDE THE DISCUSSION GROUPS (WGs, FOCUS GROUPS, TFs, ETC).....	12
1.10.7. DATA FROM EXPERT-INTERVIEWS	12
1.10.8. DATA ON BCT APPLICATIONS IMPACT ON CLIMATE CHANGE	13
1.10.9. BUSINESS MODELS	13
1.10.10. DATA FOR REALIZING FORESIGHT SCENARIOS	14
1.10.11. DATA FROM CONSENSUS BUILDING WORKSHOPS	14
1.10.12. ROADMAP.....	15
1.10.13. WHITE PAPERS.....	15
1.10.14. POLICY BRIEF.....	16
1.10.15. COLLECTION OF TOOLS, GUIDELINES, INSIGHTS TO ANIMATE AN EXISTING PLATFORM OF SERVICES.....	16
1.10.16. SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PAPERS, POSTERS, VIDEOS, OTHER PUBLICATIONS	16
1.10.17. DATA FROM GENDER POLICY PLAN MONITORING	17
2. FAIR DATA	18
2.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE AND ACCESSIBLE	18
2.2. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	19
2.3. DATA RE-USE	19
2.4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE.....	19
3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS.....	20
4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	20
4.1. ESTIMATED COSTS OF MAKING DATA FAIR.....	20
4.2. DATA MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES	20
5. DATA SECURITY	21
3. ETHICS	22
4. OTHER ISSUES.....	22

Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Definition
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work Package
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, & Resuable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PCO	Project Coordinator
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
TL	Task Leader

Executive Summary

This document deals with the research data produced, collected and preserved during the project, as well as with the way that those data will be handled after the end of the project.

It has to be clarified that this Data Management Plan (DMP) is not a fixed document but evolves during the lifespan of the project.

Being TRUSTyFOOD a CSA, the majority of the results born as public, even if a preliminary analysis on any Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) needs to be done before releasing the document. The TRUSTyFOOD project abides by the European Commission's vision that information already paid for through EC funding should not be paid for again each time it is accessed or used by the research community and that it should benefit European companies and citizens to the full. This means making publicly-funded scientific information available online, at no extra cost, to European researchers, innovative industries and citizens, while ensuring long-term preservation.

1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires the establishment and regular update of a Data Management Plan since it is not a static document but rather evolves over the project's lifespan. Accordingly, TRUSTyFOOD planned three related deliverables respectively at months 6, 18 and 36.

The consortium followed the template recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries to prepare the DMP (v1).

1.2. Guiding principles: general purpose for re-using or generating open publicly-funded scientific data

The TRUSTyFOOD project abides by the European Commission's vision¹ that “*fuller and wider access to scientific publications and data will help to:*

- *accelerate innovation (faster to market = faster growth);*
- *foster collaboration and avoid duplication of effort (greater efficiency);*
- *build on previous research results (improved quality of results);*
- *involve citizens and society (improved transparency of the scientific process).*

Indeed, “*what is at stake is the speed of scientific progress and the return on R&D investment, and in particular publicly-funded investment which has enormous potential for boosting productivity, competitiveness and growth. Improving access to scientific information is also about increasing openness and transparency, which are essential features of responsible research and innovation, and it contributes to better policy-making in a variety of areas. To ensure economic growth and to address the societal challenges of the 21st century, it is essential to optimise the circulation and transfer of scientific knowledge among key stakeholders in European research — universities, funding bodies, libraries, innovative enterprises, governments and policy-makers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and society at large*”.

“*The vision underlying the Commission's strategy on open data and knowledge circulation is that information already paid for by the public purse should not be paid for again each time it is accessed or used, and that it should benefit European companies and citizens to the full. This means making publicly-funded scientific information available online, at no extra cost, to European researchers and citizens via sustainable e-infrastructures, also ensuring long-term access to avoid losing scientific information of unique value*”.

1.3. Data Management Plan: general purpose

The DMP provides an easy overview of research data the project is expected to generate, the types and formats of this data, and how this data is processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The DMP can reflect the FAIR framework by accounting for its principles and expressing them via the use of tools.

The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how such data will be curated and preserved.

¹ European Commission (2012). Towards better access to scientific information: Boosting the benefits of public investments in research. [Source](#).

This data can either be made publicly available or not according to the Grant Agreement and to the need of the partners to preserve the IPR and related benefits derived from project results and activities.

Essentially, the Data Management Plan will answer the following main questions:

- What types of data will the project re-use and what will you re-use it for?
- What types of data will the project generate?
- What data is to be shared for the benefit of the scientific community?
- What data cannot be made available? Why?
- What format will the shared data have?
- How will this data be exploited and/or shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?
- How will this data be curated and preserved?

1.4. Specific purpose of the data generation or re-use in relation to the objectives of the project

TRUSTyFOOD is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and - as such - it is born with a strategic and policy-oriented spirit. Accordingly, most of the data collected and generated has the only purpose of being shared outside. An important role is attributed to the communication and dissemination Work Package (WP), which will convey the results as they are generated towards the target audience.

TRUSTyFOOD has been funded to clarify the current context of Blockchain applications in the agri-food sector and alleviate the confusion around the technology. The intention is to provide evidences and recommendations useful to make informed choices, both at policies level and by end users.

1.5. Basic issues that will be dealt with for the data management

The following are fundamental issues that will be addressed for the data that can be shared:

- **Dataset reference and name**
The identifier for the datasets to be produced will have the following format:
TRUSTyFOOD_ [descriptive name/related paper name]_[date of production of the data]
- **Dataset description**
Description of the data will include:
 - Its origin, nature, scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and re-use.
 - Its format
 - Tools required for data utilisation (for example specialised software)
 - Accessory information
- **Standards and metadata**
Reference to any related standards (if any). If these do not exist, an outline of how and what metadata will be created, if needed.

- **Data sharing**
Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and the definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).
- **Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup) and access modality**
Description of the procedures that will be implemented for the long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, its approximated end volume, the associated costs (if any), and how these will be covered.

1.6. Origin of Data

All data will be generated by the project partners over the course of the project, except for certain data that will be retrieved from relevant databases. More details are available in paragraphs 1.7 and 1.8.

1.7. Types of data re-used within the project

The TRUSTyFOOD project will re-use data coming from other sources, specifically for WP2 and WP4 activities.

In the context of WP2, Task 2.1, the blockchain applications will be thoroughly studied via documents at the public's disposal and analyzed in detail to extract knowledge and insights.

In task 2.2, the beneficiaries will map projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), other food-related sectors and the blockchain domain by conducting a thorough search in several databases. First, existing repositories that feature good practices throughout Europe will be consulted; these include repositories that are global, European, national or regional in scope (CORDIS for European projects; BBI-JU; ECSEL JU PRIMA database; etc). Second, when looking for information about the experiments within these digital repositories, more web links could be found to other potentially interesting experiments, which will be then further explored online.

In the context of WP4, Task 4.1 will search in several databases use cases that are relevant for climate change and agriculture/food and, in relation to GHG emission tracking, what other promising sustainability measures (apart from emission tracking) exist.

In Task 4.2, it is expected to use existing databases for carrying out an analysis of innovative business models specifically related to blockchain, as well as in Task 4.3 is the search for correlations between Blockchain Technology (BCT) applications and their transition to a sustainable, healthy and inclusive food system.

1.8. Types of data generated within the project

The TRUSTyFOOD project is expected to generate the following types of data:

- a. Database of pilots/ use cases of national, EU and International projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), other food related sectors and in the blockchain domain (WP2, T2.1/2.2)
- b. Data from the questionnaires submitted to *use cases' representatives* (WP2, T2.3)
- c. Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry and first analysis of the agri-food sector digital maturity (WP2, T2.3)
- d. Data from the *user and stakeholders' survey* (WP3, T3.1)
- e. A database of stakeholders contacts coming from the *online consultation* (WP3, T3.1)
- f. Data collected inside *Clustering group* (WP3, T3.2)
- g. Data collected inside *Policy-makers meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- h. Data collected inside *Sectoral stakeholder meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- i. Data collected inside *Local Focus Group meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- j. Data collected inside *Inter-sectoral stakeholder meetings (= Task Forces)* (WP3, T3.3)
- k. Data from *expert-interviews* (WP4, T4.1)
- l. Data on BC applications impact in climate change adaptation or mitigation in agriculture (WP4, T4.1)
- m. New business models for BCT and impact on market (WP4, T4.2)
- n. Data for realising foresight scenarios for future applications of BCT (WP4, T4.3)
- o. Data from consensus building workshops (WP5, T5.2)
- p. Roadmap (WP5)
- q. White Papers (WP5)
- r. Policy Brief (WP1 and WP5)
- s. Collection of tools, guidelines, insights to animate an existing Platform of services for BCTs users which will survive after the project's end (WP5, T5.4)
- t. Scientific and technical papers, posters, videos, other publications (WP6)
- u. Data related to gender policy plan monitoring (WP1)

1.9. Data to be shared and not

Some of the above data will be shared with the scientific community in accordance with the open data sharing principles. In particular:

- Data from category **(a)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D2.2) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website. In addition, data from category **(a)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by INOV and the other involved partners. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Because of GDPR rules, data from category **(b)** are not expected to be openly sharable. Such data will be used inside the consortium for analysing in detail the use cases and identify patterns.
- Data from category **(c)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D2.1) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website.
- Because of GDPR rules, data from categories **(d)** and **(e)** are not expected to be openly sharable. Such data will be used inside the consortium for identifying the most interesting experiences functional to the selection of stakeholders' Board members.
- Data from categories **(f)** **(g)** **(h)** **(i)** **(j)** will be shared with the scientific community, since they will feed the public Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3 which will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website.

- Data from category **(k)** are not expected to be openly sharable. Such data will be used inside the consortium for identifying, for example, which BCT-applications may improve existing practices or create new disruptive innovation in climate change & agriculture/food.
- Data from category **(l)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D4.1) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website. In addition, data from category **(l)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by FHG and the other involved partners. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Data from category **(m)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D4.2) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website. In addition, data from category **(m)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by FHG and the other involved partners. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Data from category **(n)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community for verification purposes.
- Data from categories **(o)** are not expected to be openly sharable. Such data will be used inside the consortium for reinforcing the Roadmap contents, but will not be accessible as such (apart from by the PO, being such data summarised in the Final Report).
- Data from categories **(p)** **(q)** and **(r)** will be shared with the scientific community, since they will feed the public Deliverables D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3, which will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website. In addition, through the initiatives organised in Task 6.2, specific activities will be organised for a wide visibility of these documents to the community (scientific and end users)
- Data from category **(s)** will be shared with the community. We will not share technical details on the implementation of the ePlatform, but the contents included there will be available to the public at least for some basic functions and information
- Data from category **(t)** will be shared with the community.
- Data from category **(u)** will not be shared since it is confidential information.

1.10. Details on data generated

In the sections that follow, details on the data to be shared with the community are presented.

Focus is put on:

- a) Dataset description
- b) Standards and metadata, where applicable
- c) Accessibility.

1.10.1. Database of pilots/ use cases

The data related to Database of pilots/ use cases of national, EU and International projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), in other food related sectors and in the blockchain domain are an output of WP2.

Such database will be an 'exhaustive' report on blockchain applications collected via public documents at disposal, using several open databases/repositories throughout Europe, Middle-east and North-Africa.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file. Data will be documented using a common template already used in similar studies (see FAO, 2021).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document.

Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the Database **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

In addition, once a dataset is made available on the project repository (following a publication), it will freely be available to the community as well, in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.2. Data from the questionnaires/Interviews with use cases' representatives

In the context of Task 2.3, Interviews/interactions through Questionnaires are foreseen to gather the needed information useful for analyzing the digital maturity and identifying patterns (good and bad). Iteration will focus on their own experience in BCTs application developed in the specific Pilot context.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in the Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a google form document or as a PDF file. Collected replies/data will be available in the form of completed questionnaires.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, questionnaires/Interviews minutes **will not be directly accessible** to scientific community. Such kind of data will be used for generating Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry (par. 1.10.3).

1.10.3. Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry

The data related to Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry are an output of WP2. Such data derive from an analysis and assessment done within the identified projects to evaluate working practices, implementation techniques, and remaining gaps.

The following types of data will be produced:

- Data for a public Deliverable

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community) under the form of Report.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document.

Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the Database **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.4. Data from the user and stakeholders' survey

Included are the responses of survey participants regarding their own experience with BCT application, as well as problems and challenges associated with such practices.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file. Collected replies/data will be available in the form of completed questionnaires or aggregated replies.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document.

Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, completed questionnaires **will not be directly accessible** to the scientific community. Once a dataset is made available on the project repository (following a publication), it will freely be available to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.5. A database of stakeholders contacts

The database will list different stakeholders with personal data (name, surname, organization, email, etc).

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available in Microsoft Excel format.

Standards and metadata:

Not applicable

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the database will be an internal document, which **will not be directly accessible** to scientific community.

1.10.6. Data collected inside the discussion Groups (WGs, Focus Groups, TFs, etc)

Data that come from discussions with Stakeholders will be mainly generated as an output of WP3, in particular as an output of T3.2 and T3.3. Such data will include stakeholders' experiences and opinions on BCT-related issues.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for two public Deliverables
2. Preliminary data for a Roadmap, White Papers and a Policy Brief (see par. 1.10.12-1.10.13-1.10.14)

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community) under the form of Report.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document.

Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.7. Data from expert-interviews

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of Task 4.1. Such data will include opinions from experts/stakeholders about the relationship of BCT-applications and climate change issues.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in the Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the database will be an internal document, which **will not be directly accessible** to scientific community.

1.10.8. Data on BCT applications impact on climate change

Data on BCT applications impact on climate change will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.1. Such data will come mainly from literature review, integrated by expert-interviews (see par. 1.10.7).

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in the Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

In addition, once a dataset is made available on the project repository, it will freely be available to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.9. Business Models

New business models will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.2. Such data will include the description of “new technologies” and their impact on the market and on business models in order to derive innovative business models for the incoming technologies such as BCT.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

In addition, once a dataset is made available on the project repository, it will freely be available to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section below.

1.10.10. Data for realizing foresight scenarios

Data for future scenarios will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.3. Such data will include the description of “different possible futures”, from the more modest to the more revolutionary and what would need to happen for them to materialize, who will benefit, what is the potential impact in the environment, what are the societal challenges, what are the changes required in the current institutions.

The following types of data will be produced:

- Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in the Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, data collected **might be shared** with the scientific community following **research publications**. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community for verification purposes.

1.10.11. Data from consensus building workshops

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP5, in particular as an output of consensus building workshops. Such data will include stakeholders' points of view on the current project's findings.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the database will be an internal document, which **will not be directly accessible** to the scientific community.

1.10.12. Roadmap

Data will be generated in WP1, WP3 and WP4, as well as T5.1. Such data will include recommendations for policy makers on which of the blockchain approaches are better suited to be applicable in agri-food and other food-sector domain, which business models are best for which type of entities, drawing conclusions on drivers and barriers (both technical and societal) to the further uptake of blockchain technologies and potential courses of action from the policy angle.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.13. White Papers

Data will be generated as an output of WP3 (T3.3) and WP5, in particular as an output of T5.3. Such data will include recommendations on different strategic aspects, such as:

- *Recommendations for standards in promoting blockchain technology*
- *Recommendations for Interoperability of blockchains to legacy IT*
- *Pathway for skills development (training)*

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.14. Policy Brief

Data will be generated in WP1, WP3 and WP4, as well as T5.1. Such data will include information to prepare a concise summary that can help readers understand and likely make decisions concerning government policies. Policy brief provides objective summaries of relevant research, suggest possible policy options, or go even further and argue for particular courses of action.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information regarding the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.15. Collection of tools, guidelines, insights to animate an existing Platform of services

Data will be generated as an output of task T5.3. Such data will originate from an online collaboration space providing support to Community members - e.g., idea generation, hackathons, awards and challenges, including discussion fora, wikis and blogs.

Information will be available online on the Platform, either as HTML pages or as downloadable documents in the MS Word, MS Excel or PDF format.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, we will not share technical details on the implementation of the Platform, but the contents included there will be available to the public.

1.10.16. Scientific and technical papers, posters, videos, other publications

Data from this category are intended for sharing with the research community or even the general public. All scientific publications will adhere to the green or golden “open access” model. Non-scientific publications will be freely distributed to all interested party.

Data collected is related to the developments of T6.1, which runs throughout the project. Information on the planned publications is included in the Communication and Dissemination Plan_v1, 2 and 3, which is regularly updated.

Publications will be shared in the form of pdf, video or photo files. At the moment, it is not possible to estimate the file size.

The possible use or re-use by the scientific community is provided by adhering to terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement, as well as to the terms of the publisher.

Information about tools and instruments: It is not foreseen the need to use specialised tools. Any datasets used in scientific papers will also be accessible through the same location.

Accessibility: Once a publication is made available on the project repository, it will freely be available to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section below. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.17. Data from gender policy plan monitoring

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP1, in particular as an output of T1.2. Such data will include:

- Awareness and knowledge of the project Gender Policy Plan
- Awareness and knowledge of the EU Gender Equality Strategy
- Awareness and knowledge of gender-sensitive communication guidelines
- Gender-equal working environment
- Negative discrimination
- Policies, Standards, Procedures, and Guidelines
- Knowledge of how to report gender-related issues

For more details, see D1.1.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, such data **will not be directly accessible** to the scientific community.

2. FAIR data

The European Commission has highlighted the importance of making the data produced by European-funded projects **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)**, with a view to ensuring its sound management, as well as boosting the dissemination of relevant information and the easy exchange of data within the EU state members. Thus, EU's FAIR data approach implements standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data.

The following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of TRUSTyFOOD with respect to making data findable, accessible and interoperable, as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

2.1. Making data findable and accessible

All sharable data will be published and hosted as per individual availability on the online long term repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/trustyfood/?page=1&size=20>

Partners will be instructed to upload datasets, publications, or deliverables to the repository.

The consortium will make sure that available data will be easily recoverable by any interested party. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application and the search function on the Zenodo website.

The **Zenodo** community is already acting as a one-stop-shop for data generated by EU projects and, thus, makes it easier for the data to be discovered by interested parties.

The data will be formatted as per the description of each section provided previously in this document and will be presented for access along with the necessary links to download the appropriate software tools, if necessary.

The pages will be available in the public domain, enriched with the necessary metadata and will be open to web crawlers for search engine listing, so they will be available to the public through standard web searches.

Despite the publicly available pages, the downloadable data will be presented along with possible restrictions provided in each previously described section.

Downloadable formats will be:

1. PNG, BMP, TIFF and JPEG file formats
2. ZIP and other public domain compressed archives
3. PDF formatted documents
4. WMV, MP4 or AVI formats for possible videos

All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including the Grant Number and our Project Acronym. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements (if there is no DOI from a publisher). An automatic indexing in OpenAIRE will occur as well.

Using a naming convention in a structured way makes it easier for outsiders to find results.

Zenodo will keep the data available for the lifetime of the repository, at the moment that is estimated to be at least 20 years.

Links to some of the data, especially in terms of publications, posters, videos etc. will also be directly available on the **project website**: www.trustyfood.eu. In terms of Deliverables, 15 are expected to be published and made fully accessible to the public.

In addition, Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in **CORDIS project's page** and will remain online post-project's end.

2.2. Making data interoperable

The data formats must all be non-proprietary data formats to ensure interoperability (MS Office), or in common formats that are used by people skilled in the field.

The consortium will make sure that TRUSTyFOOD data includes qualified references to other data (e.g. other data or datasets from previous research).

2.3. Data re-use

In line with the above-mentioned European Commission vision (par. 1.2), the data generated along the TRUSTyFOOD project lifespan that can be shared will be made available as Open access research data; this refers to the right to access and re-use research data. Openly accessible research data can be accessed, mined, exploited, reproduced and disseminated free of charge for the User.

2.4. Increase data re-use

To facilitate data re-use, in case of uncertain interpretation of terms used, a 'glossary' will be provided in combination with datasets.

All the data categorized as "made freely available in the public domain" in paragraph 1.10 are intended to permit the widest re-use possible. Such data produced in the project are thought to be useable by third parties along the project's lifespan and, in particular, after the end of the project. The main target audience is represented by policy-makers, the scientific community interested in BCTs and end users (farmers, food producers, and all the other players in the food system).

3. Other research outputs

Inside TRUSTyFOOD, apart from data, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica will re-use a Platform already developed in a previously funded project.

The beneficiary, in line with the FAIR principles, will not share technical details on the implementation of the ePlatform, but the contents included there will be available to the public at least for some basic functions and information.

4. Allocation of resources

4.1. Estimated costs of making data FAIR

Costs emerging from the FAIR data management process are integrated within the budget of TRUSTyFOOD.

In this respect:

- All publications related to the research conducted during the project will be submitted to scientific journals that comply with an open-access policy, and the fees will be covered by the budget allocated by the Grant;
- Zenodo is offered at no cost. TCA has created and curates the community (through the email info@trustyfood.eu), and new data might be added even after the project concludes;
- Regarding the TRUSTyFOOD project website, ownership and payments are under TCA's responsibility. The company has planned to maintain the website for a period of at least three (3) years after the completion of the project (and most probably beyond that). The related cost is relatively small per year and will be covered by the company's own funds.

4.2. Data management responsibilities

Efficient, proper and safe processing of the collected/generated data throughout TRUSTyFOOD involves the implementation of specific data management roles within the project's data management methodology and procedures. These responsibilities are outlined in this section.

□ **Project Coordinator (PCO):** The PCO, TCA, is responsible for overall data management in the framework of TRUSTyFOOD, including the elaboration of the DMP. At the same time, the PCO is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project. Finally, the PCO coordinates with Work Package and Task Leaders to determine whether and how the data produced/used by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance.

□ **Work Package Leaders (WPLs):** The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. They align with the PCO and the respective Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

□ **Task Leaders** (TLs): The TLs act as data controllers of the data collected/generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership, determining the purposes and means of processing this data as well as safeguarding its appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data produced/used through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymization techniques, the creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

5. Data security

Documents, including personal data (e.g. questionnaires, databases), will not be publicly accessible, but will remain stored in the servers of each project's partner. Each project partner will manage such data according to the internal GDPR rules in place.

In case of transfer of sensitive data from one partner to another, trusted repositories will be selected. In particular, the consortium agreed on using **Freedcamp** management platform, which provides an online collaboration tool that allows multiple users to coordinate on projects, tasks and other endeavors. A dedicated TRUSTyFOOD Folder has been created on this platform. The management of Freedcamp related to the project is under the responsibility of the coordinator (TCA).

Freedcamp makes commercially reasonable efforts to ensure that all facilities used to store and process User Data meet a high standard for security. In good faith, it exercises due diligence using reasonable business practices for IT security to ensure that systems are operated and maintained in a secure manner, and that management, operational and technical controls are employed to ensure the security of systems and data. Recognizing the changing nature of the Web, Freedcamp will continuously work with users to ensure that its Site and Services meet users' requirements for the security of systems and data.

Freedcamp has the following standard security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only) at the invitation of the project's coordinator. Further access restrictions on specific folders are enabled and Freedcamp is committed to ensuring that Data is not seen by anyone who should not have access to it.
- Encryption: The Freedcamp services support the latest recommended secure cipher suites and protocols to encrypt all traffic in transit and rest. We monitor the changing cryptographic landscape closely and work promptly to upgrade the service to respond to new cryptographic weaknesses as they are discovered and implement best practices as they evolve.
- Network protection: In addition to sophisticated system monitoring and logging, we are running Security-Enhanced Linux (SELinux) in enforcing mode. Firewalls are configured according to industry best practices and unnecessary ports are blocked by configuration with AWS Security Groups.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevent and/or register possible manipulation of data.

The type and number of tools and services will depend on which Paid Plan User. Freedcamp's Free plan is provided at zero cost to all Users; its essential features are considered enough for TRUSTyFOOD data management. No resources are thus expected to be spent for storage, even if the repository allows for upgrades. In the case of need, TCA is in charge of sustaining such kind of expenses.

For data shared, CERN maintains a very strict security policy around data stored on its servers Zenodo that needs to stay confidential. For public data, security can be less strict. For the preservation of the public files, Zenodo has: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/>

3. Ethics

In the case of data sharing, informed consent and long-term preservation will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data.

4. Other issues

Not applicable